

The Rheumatic Valvulopathies in Schools in Burkina Faso

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Abstract:

Introduction: The purpose of our study was to determine the prevalence of rheumatic valve diseases in the primary schools Provincial Directorate of Education National (DPENA) of Kadiogo.

Patients and methods: This was a prevalence study Over a period of 8 months carrying on primary school students from all constituencies Basic Education (CEB) of the Kadiogo Provincial Directorate of National Education. We conducted clinical and paraclinical screening with a representative sample of this population. **Results:** Our sample was 1519 students from 50 schools spread over 26 CEBs. The sex ratio Was 0.94. Were included in the study the students of the tranche of age of 5 to 16 years old. The

social level low economic was predominant and was found in 72.46% of cases. Associated comorbidities were dental caries (17.05%), angina/tonsillar hypertrophy (2.57%). The ultrasound prevalence of valvulopathies Probable according to the classification of the World Federation of the Heart was 7.24% with no significant difference between the sexes. **Conclusion:** Rheumatic valve diseases are still endemic in school-age children in developing countries. The need for early detection and management of these conditions is necessary to improve the health of future adult populations in Burkina Faso.

Keywords: heart disease, rheumatic valve diseases, clinical and paraclinical screening, associated comorbidities, early detection.

Introduction

Valvulopathies are of acquired heart disease relatively frequent thus constituting a public health problem in both developed and developing countries (Nkomo, et al., 2006; WHO, 2004). In the African context, these valvulopathies are most often of rheumatic origin with high mortality. They follow infection with group A beta-hemolytic streptococci. The prevalence of these rheumatic valve diseases was estimated between 3.4 and 16.5 % in 42 African countries and the number of children with these valvular diseases varies between 23,900 and 115,800 in Burkina Faso (Weinberg, et al., 2016). Few studies in extra hospital have evaluated of the prevalence of these rheumatic valve diseases in schools in Burkina Faso. This is why we propose to determine the prevalence of these valvulopathies in the primary schools of Kadiogo (central region) with a view to proposing a better strategy of support both curatively and preventively.

Methodology

Patients

We conducted a study of prevalence at collection data a prospective foresight over a period of eight months from March 1 to October 31. The sampling has concerned only primary school students, from the Class of the Preparatory Course 1^E Year (CP1) to that of the Middle Course 2^E Year (CM2) and was included in this study all those students whose parents have given their consent. Were not included in the study, the students elderly under 6 years old or more than 15 years or whose parents had not given their consent. Were excluded from the study, the students who did not respond to invitation to undergo cardiac echocardiography. To ensure the drawing of a representative sample, the use of a two-degree stratified survey is was imposed. The primary unit (UP) was the school and the secondary unit (US) was the student. The size of the sample being related to the accuracy of the indicators sought, we have used so the following formula:

$$n_0 \geq \frac{z_{\alpha}^2 f(1-f)}{l^2} * g * (1 + t) \quad (1)$$

With n_0 = Sample size,

z_{α} = 1.96 = coefficient of accuracy,

α = 0.05 = risk of error,

f = 0.5 = appr value oximative of the key variable of the survey,

g = 2 = Cluster effect,

l = 5% = Accuracy of results T

t = 1% = Early non-response rate.

After calculation, $n_0 \geq 776$ students to be shot in 26 schools. In order to obtain a much more representative study, the number of primary units was increased to 50 and the total sample size carried until to 1519 students. The screening has consisted of the on-site collection of settings of the examination physical such that the auscultation cardiac to detect a breath. One and only doctor (Cardiologist in Training) was committed to the task. The students in whom the breath had been found were advised and received an information note to the parents to prepare for the screening phase to the imaging. On the map organic that, a dowise of ASLO (Antistreptolysines O) has been realized and concern all students in whom the auscultation had found a heart murmur. The biological tests were validated by a pharmacist biologist, and ultrasound reports validated by a cardiologist with Inter-university diploma of echocardiography. The data have been processed and analyzed using the Epi Info and Excel 2011 software. A value of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered significant for all tests.

Operational Definitions

Socio-economic level: The low socio-economic level concerned monthly incomes of less than 50,000 FCFA, the of average concerned in come between 50,000 and 250,000 CFA, and the high level above 250000 FCFA.

Positive ASLO: Higher titre 200IU/L according to the technical specifications of the laboratory.

Dilation of the cavities with echocardiography: The normal ultrasound thresholds were according to the tables used in the cardiology department of the CHU-YO defining these normal values according to the size in the child.

Pulmonaire arterial hypertension (PAH): Defined for a systolic pulmonary arterial pressure greater than 35 mm Hg.

Data collection was made through two forms, one for ultrasound examinations. The investigation team was made up of doctors, pharmacists, medical students, nurses, laboratory technicians, and primary school teachers. The data analysis was done using the Epi-Info version 7 and Excel 2007 software.

Ethical Considerations

We have received the authorization of the Kadiogo Provincial Directorate of National Education (DPENA). Before administering the

questionnaire, we have also obtained a Consent of Parents of the students. They were explained that they could withdraw their consent at any time in the study. The personal data of the respondents will under no circumstances be disclosed to a third party and the use of the questionnaire will be done anonymously.

Results

Social-Demographic Data

Our study has on a sample of 1519 students spread over 50 primary schools (Figure 1) of the DPENA Kadiogo with 847 students from public schools (55.76%) and 672 students from private schools (44.24%). The average age of Students was 9.5 years old with extremes ranging from 5 to 16 years. The age group from 5 to 10 years old represented 65.50% of the study population (n=995) and that from 11 to 16 years old 34.5% (n=524). The sex ratio was 0.94. The students' living environment was characterized by a low socioeconomic level in 72.46% of cases, an average sibling of 4.5 children, and an urban residence in 67.80% of cases.

Figure 1. Flow Chart

Clinical Data

All the students screened had good apparent health without any Cardiac symptoms. At the end of the examination physical, Fever was observed in 63 students, or 4.15% of cases. Oropharyngeal disorders were represented by dental caries in 259 children (17.05%) and angina/tonsillar hypertrophy in 39 children (2.57%). Cardiac auscultation recorded the presence of breath in 6.45% of cases (n=98).

Figures 2 and 3 show respectively. The geographical distribution of students present a breath that has benefited from an ultrasound

screening And the distribution Of students with probable valve diseases within the Kadiogo DPENA. These murmurs were systolic in 97 cases and diastolic in one case. seventy-two (72) echocardiographies were carried out because 26 students with breath did not respond to the summons (Figure 4). A total of 52 students out of 98 having presented a heart murmur benefited from a blood sample, i.e. 53.06% of this subgroup. The ASLO rate was higher than 200 IU/L in 12 cases or 23.07% of cases. There was no statistically significant difference between the boys and girls subgroups (CI: 0.1753— 2.3825).

Figure 2. Mapping of Screening Sites

Figure 3. The Geographical Distribution of Students with a Clinical Breath Who have Benefited from Ultrasound Screening

Figure 4. The Geographical Repair of Students with Probable Valvular Disease within the Kadiogo DPENA

Echocardiographic Data

Ultrasound exploration (Table 1) have mountain a good systolic function of the left ventricle In all 72 students screened with an EVGF varying from 60 % At 86%. Morphological anomalies valves were represented by mitral valve thickening in 30 cases (41.66%), and a restriction of the play of the small mitral valve in 5 cases (6.94%). Flow analyses, without prejudging the pathological nature or not, made it possible to find mitral insufficiency in 27 cases, tricuspid insufficiency in 53 cases, aortic insufficiency in one case and pulmonary insufficiency in 16 cases. No cases of valve narrowing have been noted. The left atrium was dilated in 15 cases

(20.83%) and this dilation was significantly associated with the presence of probable valvular disease ($p < 0.01$). The left ventricle was dilated in 3 cases. We noted a HTAP in 6 cases and this one I was statistically associated with the presence of probable valvular disease significantly ($p < 0.01$). The analysis of ultrasound data made it possible to classify valvulopathies according to the criteria of the World Federation of the Heart. Thus, there were 11 probable rheumatic valvulopathies, zero certain rheumatic valvulopathy, and 61 cardiac ultrasounds within normal limits. The ultrasound prevalence of valvulopathies was therefore 7.24‰ with 6 boys and 5 girls ($P = 0.69$).

Table 1. Distribution of Children with Heart Murmur According to Echocardiographic Abnormalities.

	Probable valve diseases	No valvulopathy	total
IM	10	17	27
IT	6	47	53
IA	1	0	1
IP	3	13	16
Thickened valves	7	23	30
Dilated OG	6	9	15
VG dilate	1	2	3
OD dilate	1	0	1
VD dilate	1	0	1
HTAP	2	4	6
FEVG	0,70	0,72	NA

Note: MR : miral regurgitation ,TR : tricuspid regurgitation ,AR : aortic regurgitation , PR :pulmonary regurgitaion LA: left atrium , LV : left ventricule, RA:rigth atrium, RV : right ventrile

Discussion

Epidemiological Characteristics

Our methodology differs from that used by some authors who have identified an urban or rural population to perform screening (Allen, & Gillespie, 2001; De Onis, et al., 2007). However, it was comparable to new ultrasound screening methods that used the random method to determine their study population on the prevalence of rheumatic valve diseases (Health and Social Agency of New Caledonia, 2016; Figueroa, et al., 2001). The size of our sample was 1519 students and comparable to that reported by Moyen et al. in Congo (De Onis, et al., 2007), but lower than the one reported by Bertrand in Côte d'Ivoire (Allen, & Gillespie, 2001). The relatively small size of our sample is explained by the constraints associated with the lack of funding for the study. The average age of our students was 9.5 years. This average was lower than that reported by Marijon and al in Cambodia (Corsenac, Fauchier, & Rouchon, 2014), and Kane and al in Senegal (Carapetis, Parr, & Cherian, 2006). The age range of 5 to 16 years was comparable to that found in other African countries (Allen, & Gillespie, 2001; Health and Social Agency of New Caledonia, 2016). The valvulopathies probable were predominant in the subgroup of 11 to 16 years of age. This supports observations that rheumatic valve lesions are diagnosed at an older age, especially adolescence and young adulthood (Carapetis, Parr, & Cherian, 2006; Barsaoui, 2005; Goeh Akue, et al., 2013). Our study included more girls than boys with a sex ratio of 0.94. This was different from the reported observations in other school studies where the male gender was predominant (Corsenac, Fauchier, & Rouchon, 2014; Carapetis, Parr, & Cherian, 2006; Barsaoui, 2005). This higher number of girls could be explained by the fact that this gender is predominant in the school staff of the Kadiogo DPENA that served as a base for our sampling. However, there was no statistically significant difference between the sexes in students with valvular diseases. The low socioeconomic level was predominant in our

sample but also among those diagnosed as probable valvulopathies. This observation has also been reported by other authors in Africa (De Onis, et al., 2007; Health and Social Agency of New Caledonia, 2016). It reinforces the fact that rheumatic valve diseases are the prerogative of poor families living in a certain promiscuity (Beaton, et al., 2012; Kane, et al., 2013).

Echocardiographic Parameters

The ultrasound prevalence of valvulopathies rheumatism was 7.24‰ in our study. This prevalence is in the range of recent estimated prevalences in country Africans who is located between 3.4 and 16.5 ‰ (High Health Authority, 2012). The ultrasound prevalence found in our study was much higher than that reported by Bertrand et al in Ivoir coast which was 1.90 ‰ (Allen, & Gillespie, 2001). These low prevalences could be explained by the fact that these studies involved students in urban areas where the prevalence of rheumatic diseases is generally lower than in rural areas. Our ultrasound prevalence is much lower than the estimates for Burkina, which predict a prevalence between 23.9 and 205.7 ‰ according to the estimation models used (High Health Authority, 2012). She is also lower than the prevalence reported by Marijon et al. (Corsenac, Fauchier, & Rouchon, 2014) in Mozambique (30.4‰) and Cambodia (21.5‰). This relatively low prevalence could be explained by the use in our study of the 2012 criteria of the federation World ration of the heart instead of the WHO criteria and the 2008 criteria of this same federation. Indeed, the 2012 criteria would increase the specificity of confirmed rheumatic heart disease, to raise the threshold of positivity of probable valvular diseases, and to reduce the rate of false positives due to minor changes resulting from physiological valve regurgitation (D'Ortenzio, Barou, & Rouchon, 2012). The high urban proportion of our sample could also explain the low prevalence of rheumatic valve diseases in our study. However, the use of the criteria of the World Federation of the Heart for ultrasound diagnosis should not obscure cases of possible valvular diseases not responding to the

pathological classification according to these criteria. Indeed, authentic incipient rheumatic valve diseases could be screened in the follow-up of children with minimal mitral leakage and high ASLO titers. This underlines the need for regular follow-up of school-age children in order to screen and take care of any rheumatic valve disease as soon as possible.

Others Data Paraclinics

Most studies Screening for valve diseases in schools did not include the biological components, including the dosage of ASLO. However, Bertrand et al. (Allen, & Gillespie, 2001) in Ivoir coast found positive ASLO in 19.5% of their population in schools. As Hospital studies have addressed these biological aspects, including the corollary between valvulopathies and ASLO title. Thus Naré et al. (Zabsonre, et al., 1995) in Ouagadougou found a high rate of ASLO titer in 64.5% of rheumatic heart diseases. Zabsonré et al. in Abidjan (Naré, 2002) found 74.5% of high titles. Our study was about to offer a blood sample to all children with heart murmur at auscultation. The high titre of ASLOs was found in 20% of probable valvular diseases, which is comparable to the rate found by Bertrand et al in Ivoir Coast. It is also lower than the rates found in other hospital studies. Our low rate would be explained by the fact that many students in our sample were not in a period of rheumatic evolution or in a period close to a streptococcal infection.

Limitations of the study. The main limitation of our study was the impossibility of performing ultrasounds in our children in our sample.

Conclusion

Rheumatic valvular diseases are endemic cardiovascular diseases in Burkina Faso. Our study revealed that the prevalence of his conditions in primary school is not negligible within the DPENA Kadiogo. This study is one of the first surveys on valvular diseases in schools in Burkina Faso and did not allow systematic ultrasound screening of our entire sample. It's why it would be of great epidemiological interest to conduct other

population studies, especially in rural areas, in order to determine a more accurate prevalence of these conditions in children and adolescents.

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